

Elevating natural science learning achievement: Cooperative learning and learning interest

Mamik Suendarti, Virgana Virgana

Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, Post Graduate Program, Universitas Indraprasta PGRI Jakarta, Jakarta, Indonesia

Article Info

Article history:

Received Nov 11, 2021

Revised Dec 30, 2021

Accepted Feb 22, 2022

Keywords:

Jigsaw
Learning achievement
Learning style
Problem solving
Side effect

ABSTRACT

Natural science learning achievement is an essential factor in learning outcomes. This research investigated an experimental study that aimed to improve concept science test result in online learning through Jigsaw cooperative learning model and learning style. The research involved the sample of 80 students from junior high school in South Jakarta, Indonesia divided into two groups: the experimental class and the class control. Raw data were statistically analyzed using the two-way variance technique at the .05 significance level. The findings revealed an effect between cooperative learning on natural science learning achievement, learning interest in natural science learning achievement, and interaction between cooperative learning and learning interest in natural science learning achievement. As a result, cooperative learning type Jigsaw shows a significant impact and had a good test result on natural science learning achievement. Therefore, the research suggests that Jigsaw cooperative learning is well suited to use as a learning model among junior high school students based on effect size test results.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Mamik Suendarti
Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences
Post Graduate Program, Universitas Indraprasta PGRI Jakarta
Nangka Street no. 58c, East Tanjung, South Jakarta, Indonesia
Email: suendarti@gmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

In general, studying natural sciences at the junior level is insufficient due to a lack of understanding of scientific concepts. Poor learning design contributes to poor learning outcomes in the natural sciences [1]. Low performance in science learning is caused by two factors: internal factors in students such as health, interests, and intelligence, and external factors beyond the student's control such as home environment, community, teachers and learning models, and learning facilities [2]. The Pisa 2018 results of Indonesian science obtained a score of 396, while the average world score was 489, and China was ranked first with a score of 590 [3].

The data show that Indonesian students' mastery of concept science is unsatisfactory; thus, this research uses learning activities based on cooperative learning that interacts with learning interests. The availability of various learning models has improved students' cognitive and affective learning [4]. Students become bored due to a monotonous learning strategy, resulting in poor learning outcomes [5]. One of the results of a lack of learning interest is a low learning achievement [6]. The cooperative learning models provide students with learning experiences that can enable them to learn better [7]. The application of these models' trains students to express their opinions and collaborate in personal interactions in group processes [8]. Students have different learning styles [9]; motivation, engagement and learning interests in a subject varies as well [10].

Learning achievement correlated to the results of students' efforts in achieving maximal learning outcomes [11]. The effectiveness of learning is evaluated with continuous assessment or academic test, under the achievement of applicable success standards [12], [13]. Learning achievement is one of the important components of learning in an educational system [14]. High learning performance students generally correlate with high learning attitudes and desires [15], [16]. In other words, that learning achievement results from students' efforts in learning with an evaluation that achieves a certain passing grade.

A cooperative learning model is a learning strategy that divides students into groups to discuss and work together in understanding the subject matter guided by the teacher to achieve learning goals [17], [18]. Cooperative learning type Jigsaw is a learning model involving students thinking actively about abilities, emotions, and skills [8]. Jigsaw cooperative learning in the classroom can improve the understanding and discovery of the concept of the material studied [19]. In this collaborative method learning model each student is part of groups: the original and the expert group. In the expert group, each student has a material responsibility [20]. The expert group comes from members of the original group, who have the information to be explained to the original group [21].

One of the learning models for increasing student involvement in learning is problem-solving [22]. It is a learning model that focuses on problems that students must solve [23]. This is also a learning method that trains students to solve problems and provides students with the necessary mental schemes to use the concept of thinking at a higher level [24]. A problem-solving learning model is essentially a learning model that focuses on the material associated with the problem, which students must solve with cognitive abilities learned in advance.

Students show learning interest to comprehend the subject matter [25]. Students' learning interests manifest as positive learning habits [10]. Appropriate learning models are associated with increased student learning interest [26]. Students show learning interest by studying more diligently [27], [28]. Students who would like to learn will spend their free time studying natural science wherever they are [29]. Students show learning interest by studying hard, doing tasks, and always attempting to understand the subject matter delivered by the teachers in the classroom.

Interaction Jigsaw and learning interest is to find out the difference in the average value of two categories. There is a significant interactive influence of the Jigsaw learning model with learning interest [30]. If there is an interactive influence then continue the Tukey test. Tukey test in ANOVA is to determine the level of trust [31]. Concerning the background of the research above, the following research questions are formulated to determine the purpose of this research and show the importance of natural science learning achievement in learning outcomes: i) Is cooperative learning affecting students' performance in science learning achievement?; ii) Is there an effect of learning interest on students' natural science learning outcomes?; iii) Is there a relationship between the interaction influence of cooperative learning model and learning interest students' science on learning achievement?

The determination of the effect size of Jigsaw cooperative learning is a novel aspect of this study, which includes the research hypotheses: i) Cooperative learning has a significant impact on natural science learning outcomes (h_1); ii) Natural science learning achievement is significantly influenced by learning interest (h_2); iii) Cooperative learning and a learning interest interaction have a significant effect on natural science learning achievement (h_3).

2. RESEARCH METHOD

With a research sample of 80, this study was an experiment in which two study groups of students from class VIII junior high school in South Jakarta, Indonesia were given different types of treatment. The first group was the experimental group, which received natural science instruction via cooperative learning Jigsaw. The second group served as a control group for natural science learning using cooperative learning problem-solving. Because the research variable is treatment, a two-way ANOVA was used in the study. Each class was then divided into teams of two students based on their level of learning interest: high and low. Tests were given to both classes with the same instrument at the end of the treatment, and the results were analyzed and compared. Google Classroom has been used for learning activities, as well as the division of student groups, namely the initial group and experts. At each session, teachers can assist with group activities and provide directions as needed.

For learning interest, a Likert scale has been used as research instruments in questionnaires, and natural science learning achievement, an essay test with 20 questions about Household Chemistry; Uses and Side Effects of Chemicals; Natural and Artificial Chemicals. The study was carried out in the odd semesters of 2021/2022. Deployment of instrument learning was accomplished by using a Google Form and instrument essay tests and answers through a WhatsApp group. The research instruments are tested for validity and reliability, the factorial research designs 2 x 2 treatments by level, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Research design

Learning interest		Cooperative learning		Total
High	(B1)	Jigsaw (A1) A1B1	Problem solving (A2) A2B1	$\sum B$ $\sum B1$
Low	(B2)	A1B2	A2B2	$\sum B2$
	$\sum A$	$\sum A1$	$\sum A2$	AxB

Note:

A1B1: Natural science learning achievement score high learning interest students with Jigsaw

A1B2: Natural science learning achievement score of low learning interest students with Jigsaw

A2B1: Natural science learning achievement score of high learning interest students with problem solving

A2B2: Natural science learning achievement score of low learning interest students with problem solving

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the requirements for data analysis in research, the data must be normal and homogeneous. Data normality testing with the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov SPSS 24 test with $n=80$ in Normal Parameters at Asymp. Sig.(2-tailed) $>.05$, the test conclusion distribution is normal. The variance test homogeneity result employs a Levene population with a significance level ($=0.05$), concluding homogeneous data with Sig. $>.05$, as shown in Table 2 while Table 3 shows the analysis results of testing with the ANOVA SPSS program showed that Sig. $<.05$ proved all hypotheses were significant.

Table 2. Test of homogeneity of variances

Dependent variables: Natural science achievement			
Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
2.047	3	76	.114

Tests the null hypothesis that the error variance of the dependent variable is equal across groups

a. Design: Intercept + A + B + A * B

Table 3. Tests of between-subjects effects

Dependent Variables: Natural science learning achievement						
Source	Type III Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.	
Corrected model	81.737 ^a	3	27.246	6.167	.001	
Intercept	501019.513	1	501019.513	113410.225	.000	
A	35.113	1	35.113	7.948	.006	
B	27.613	1	27.613	6.250	.015	
A * B	19.013	1	19.013	4.304	.041	
Error	335.750	76	4.418			
Total	501437.000	80				
Corrected Total	417.487	79				

a. R Squared = .196 (Adjusted R Squared = .164)

The first findings from the research intended to answer the first research question: the influence of cooperative learning on students' performance in science education at Jakarta's 8th grade Junior High Schools. According to the results of the analysis of the table test effects between the subjects in Table 3, which state that the p-value for the cooperative training model was .006 (0.05), there was a significant difference in natural science learning achievement using the learning model cooperative Jigsaw and Problem-solving. The Jigsaw learning model performed better than the type problem-solving model, with a score of $79.80 > 79.48$. The findings of this study are relevant, indicating that cooperative learning strategy has a positive influence on students' achievement at STIKON Surabaya [32]. Cooperative learning strategies positively affect student achievement in Aceh Besar senior high schools [33]. According to meta-analysis research, cooperative learning affects students' learning achievement [34].

The second results are to answer the second research question: The influence of learning interest on students' natural science learning outcomes, 8th grade Junior High schools in Jakarta. The analysis results on the table Test of Between-Subject Effects in Table 3 notes that the p-value for learning interest was .015 (0.05), there was a significant difference in natural science learning achievement using learning interest. The average score on the learning interest test (High and Low) was $A1B1=79.90$; $A2B1=79.55$ and $A2B1=79.70$; $A2B2=77.40$. Previous research has found that learning interest positively affects the chemistry of learning outcomes in Jogjakarta public high schools [26]. Learning interest has a positive effect on learning achievement in Pangkajene elementary schools [10].

The third results are used to answer the third research question: the interaction influence of cooperative learning model and learning interest students on learning achievement, 8th grade Junior High schools in Jakarta. Based on the analysis results on the table Test of Between-Subject Effects in Table 3, which notes that the p-value for learning interest was .000 (0.05), it means that interactive, cooperative learning and learning interest significantly influenced natural science learning achievement. Cooperative learning and learning interest had an interactive influence on students' learning achievement at Kebumen Central Java Junior High School [35]. Similarly, based on Table 3, it is possible to conclude that the use of cooperative learning and learning interest contributes 19.6 % to students' learning achievement at a junior high school in South Jakarta.

Based on the third result, the search for significance influence requires further tests then conducted in post-hoc or Tukey tests on variables. Then the results of Tukey test calculations with SPSS 24. Table 4 shows the Post-hoc or Tukey score tests in the natural sciences. Based on the Tukey test result, the pair has a meaningful difference at the .05 was: A1B1 and A2B2; A1B2 and A2B2; A2B1 and A2B2; A2B2 and A1B1; A2B2 and A1B2; A2B2 and A2B1 because they have sig values. <.05.

Table 4. Multiple comparisons

Dependent variables: Natural science achievement						
Tukey HSD						
(I) Post hoc	(J) Post hoc	Mean difference (I-J)	Std. error	Sig.	95% Confidence interval	
					Lower bound	Upper bound
A1B1	A1B2	.20	.665	.990	-1.55	1.95
	A2B1	.35	.665	.952	-1.40	2.10
	A2B2	2.50*	.665	.002	.75	4.25
A1B2	A1B1	-.20	.665	.990	-1.95	1.55
	A2B1	.15	.665	.996	-1.60	1.90
	A2B2	2.30*	.665	.005	.55	4.05
A2B1	A1B1	-.35	.665	.952	-2.10	1.40
	A1B2	-.15	.665	.996	-1.90	1.60
	A2B2	2.15*	.665	.010	.40	3.90
A2B2	A1B1	-2.50*	.665	.002	-4.25	-.75
	A1B2	-2.30*	.665	.005	-4.05	-.55
	A2B1	-2.15*	.665	.010	-3.90	-.40

Based on observed means.

The error term is Mean Square (Error) = 4.418

*. The mean difference is significant at the .05 level.

The following conclusions can show the additional test described above based on the test information in Table 4: First, there was Jigsaw and a high-interest learning group (A1B1) and a low-interest learning group (A1B2), and the Mean Difference is (.20)., Since the difference between the scores of (A1B1) and (A1B2) did not have a significant value $.990 > .05$, this implies that there is no difference between (A1B1) and (A1B2). Students are not required to master specific cognitive abilities; the Jigsaw learning model prioritizes responsibility in learning so that students with high and low learning interests share the same responsibility. In this case, Jigsaw cooperative learning is a learning model in which students are responsible for the subject matter. Students must understand the learning material as simply as possible and be able to explain it to their friends [36].

Second, it shows that the mean Difference amounted to (2.30) in the problem solving cooperatively and high-interest learning group (A2B1) and the problem solving cooperative learning and low-interest learning group (A2B2), indicating that the difference between the scoring average of (A2B1) and (A2B2) was a significance value $.010 < 0.05$, implying that (A2B1) and (A2B2) differ significantly. Students who are disinterested in class lack the motivation to learn [37]. When compared to students who are enthusiastic about learning, this will result in lower learning achievement.

Third, in the Jigsaw and a high-interest learning group (A1B1) and a problem-solving learning group and high-interest learning (A2B1), the Mean Difference is (.35), indicating that the difference between the scores of (A1B1) and (A1B2) was not significant. A significance value $.952 > .05$ can be interpreted (A1B1) and (A1B2) did not have a significant value. These findings can be explained by the fact that students who are enthusiastic about learning in any learning model will work hard to learn. Interest in learning has the ability to control one's desire to learn [37].

Fourth, it discovered that the mean Difference amounted to (2.30) in the Jigsaw cooperative learning and low-interest learning group (A1B2) and the problem-solving cooperative learning and low-interest learning group (A2B2), indicating that the difference between the scoring average of (A1B2) and (A2B2) was a significance value $.005 < 0.05$, implying that (A1B2) and (A2B2) differ significantly. This demonstrates

students who have a low interest in learning that Jigsaw method is superior to problem-solving, even though their interest in learning is also low.

To achieve the best learning outcomes, a teacher must consider the size effect of the method when selecting a learning model. Furthermore, to avoid misinterpretation, learning models should be used first to familiarize students with the new method. Based on experimental data collection, we will calculate the use of Jigsaw and problem-solving in learning activities in this research. The magnitude of the effect size, defined as the strength of the relationship in test results between the control and experiment classes [35]. Becker further said that effect size is defined as the difference in the average score of test results from the experimental and control classes divided by the combined standard deviation [36]. Becker went on to say that the effect size should be calculated using the formula Effect Size: $D = \frac{X_e - X_k}{\text{Spooled } D}$ with D =Effect Size Cohen; X_e =Mean Experimental group; X_k =Mean Group control; Spooled=Combined Standard Deviation. While the Spooled D value uses the formula $= \sqrt{\frac{(n1-1)sd_1^2 + (n2-1)sd_2^2}{n1+n2}}$; the large classification of small effect size is: $D < .15$ (Negligible); $.15 < D \leq .40$ (small effect size); $.40 < D \leq .75$ (enough); $.75 < D \leq 1.10$ (High enough); $1.10 < D \leq 1.45$ (high); $D > 1.45$ (very high) [38].

From the data in Table 5, it shows a value of $D = .6037$ ($.40 < D \leq .75$: enough) with the conclusion that the Jigsaw cooperative learning model has enough effect size. Thus, Jigsaw cooperative learning can be used as a natural science learning model in junior high schools.

Table 5. Descriptive statistics

Dependent variables: Natural science achievement				
Cooperative learning	Learning interest	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Jigsaw	High	79.90	2.654	20
	Low	79.70	1.949	20
	Total	79.80	2.301	40
Problem solving	High	79.55	1.820	20
	Low	77.40	1.875	20
	Total	78.48	2.124	40
Total	High	79.73	2.253	40
	Low	78.55	2.218	40
	Total	79.14	2.299	80

4. CONCLUSION

The use of Jigsaw learning models is an effort to increase understanding of a subject. Based on the theory, Jigsaw cooperative learning can increase students' learning activities in the classroom that emphasize the learning process, although there is an influence of learning interest in achieving learning outcomes. The study concluded that Jigsaw cooperative learning is the appropriate learning model to be implemented in junior high school compared to the method of learning problem solving. Jigsaw revealed better test results and a reasonably good effect size.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Jufrida, W. Kurniawan, A. Astalini, D. Darmaji, D. A. Kurniawan, and W. A. Maya, "Students' attitude and motivation in mathematical physics," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, vol. 8, no. 3, pp. 401–408, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v8i3.20253.
- [2] I. Mushtaq and S. N. Khan, "Factors Affecting Students' Academic Performa," *Annual Conference of the North American Fuzzy Information Processing Society - NAFIPS*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 2648–2652, 2012, doi: 10.1109/nafips.2001.943641.
- [3] OECD, "PISA 2018 Result," www.oecd.org/about/publishing/corrigenda.htm, vol. 3, no. 2018, pp. 1–25, 2019.
- [4] M. Sudin, C. Hermawan, O. Rosfiani, W. Ristiawati, and S. Hasanah, "Improve Mathematics Pedagogical Content Knowledge and Verbal Communication Skills through Cooperative Learning Type Jigsaw," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1764, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1764/1/012094.
- [5] S. Sunaryadi, "Improving Learning Achievement by Using Jigsaw Technique in Science Learning focusing on the topic of Preservation of Living Organisms on the Fifth Grade Semester I of SDN 2 Tribungan," *Pancaran Pendidikan*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 93–107, 2020, doi: 10.25037/pancaran.v8i1.236.
- [6] J. Jufrida, F. R. Basuki, W. Kurniawan, M. D. Pangestu, and O. Fitaloka, "Scientific literacy and science learning achievement at junior high school," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, vol. 8, no. 4, pp. 630–636, 2019, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v8i4.20312.
- [7] E. C. Alabekee, A. Samuel, and S. D. Osaat, "Effect Of cooperative learning strategy on students learning experience and achievements in mathematics," *International Journal of Education Learning and Development*, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 67–75, 2015.
- [8] F. P. Soedimardjono and P. P., "Cooperative Learning Model with Jigsaw Type Improves Students' Sciences Process Skills and Learning Outcomes," *JPI (Jurnal Pendidikan Indonesia)*, vol. 10, no. 1, p. 172, 2021, doi: 10.23887/jpi-undiksha.v10i1.25203.
- [9] M. M. Nahla, "The Importance of Learning Styles in Education," *Institute for Learning Styles Journal*, vol. 1, no. Fall 2014, pp.

- 19–27, 2014.
- [10] A. Syamsuddin, R. Babo, Sulfasyah, and S. Rahman, "Mathematics learning interest of students based on the difference in the implementation of model of thematic learning and character-integrated thematic learning," *European Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 581–591, 2021, doi: 10.12973/EU-JER.10.2.581.
- [11] P. Singh, "Academic Achievement in Mathematics in Relation to Study-Habits Abstract :," *International Journal of Innovative Research & Development*, vol. 4, no. 5, pp. 302–306, 2015.
- [12] A. K. Singh and J. Kaur, "Achievement Motivation and Locus of Control as Predictors of Achievement Motivation and Locus of Control As Predictors of Academic Achievement Motivation Among Students," *Suraj Punj Journal For Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. 9, no. 4, pp. 204–215, 2019, doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24338.71369.
- [13] E. Karadağ, "The factors effecting student achievement: Meta-analysis of empirical studies," *The Factors Effecting Student Achievement: Meta-Analysis of Empirical Studies*, no. May 2017, pp. 1–337, 2017, doi: 10.1007/978-3-319-56083-0.
- [14] B. I. Ejioji-okeke and N. N. C. Samuel, "Achievement Motivation And Locus Of Control As Predictors Of Secondary School Students ' Academic Achievement In Chemistry In Enugu State , Nigeria," *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 27–34, 2021, doi: 10.9790/7388-1104052734.
- [15] C. Shieh, "A Study on Information Technology Integrated Guided Discovery Instruction towards Students' Learning Achievement and Learning Retention," *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education*, vol. 12, no. 7, pp. 833–842, 2016, doi: 10.12973/eurasia.2015.1554a.
- [16] N. Hanifah, A. Salam, and D. Dewantara, "The Effect of Adversity Quotient and Attitudes of Students on the Student ' s Physical Learning Achievements," *Jurnal Pena Sains*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 1–7, 2021, doi: 10.21107/jps.v8i1.9221.
- [17] R. M. Gillies, "Cooperative learning: Review of research and practice," *Australian Journal of Teacher Education*, vol. 41, no. 3, pp. 39–54, 2016, doi: 10.14221/ajte.2016v41n3.3.
- [18] S. Kasyadi, M. Lapasau, and V. Virgana, "Enhancing learning outcome in integral through Online teaching based during COVID-19 pandemic," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series PAPER*, vol. 1663, no. 2020, pp. 1–7, 2020, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1663/1/012059.
- [19] Maison, T. Tant, D. A. Kurniawan, W. Sukarni, Erika, and R. Hoyi, "Assessing students' attitudes towards physics through the application of inquiry and jigsaw cooperative learning models in high schools," *International Journal of Instruction*, vol. 14, no. 4, pp. 439–450, 2021, doi: 10.29333/iji.2021.14426a.
- [20] A. M. Haftador, F. Shirazi, and Z. Mohebbi, "Online class or flipped-jigsaw learning? Which one promotes academic motivation during the COVID-19 pandemic?," *BMC Medical Education*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 1–8, 2021, doi: 10.1186/s12909-021-02929-9.
- [21] A. A. Atallah, M. F. Ben Hassen, A. B. Musa, M. R. Bougherira, and N. Frih, "The application of the Jigsaw cooperative learning technique in mapping concepts of nuclear radiation in diagnosis and therapy," *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, vol. 20, no. 7, pp. 151–174, 2021, doi: 10.26803/IJLTER.20.7.9.
- [22] Y. Lestari, M. Rahmad, and Z. Zulfarina, "Needs Analysis of Problem Solving Based Learning Video Development to Train Students' Concept Understanding," *Jurnal Pendidikan Sains (Jps)*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 81, 2021, doi: 10.26714/jps.9.1.2021.81-90.
- [23] Y. Yusri, "The Effects of Problem Solving, Project-Based Learning, Linguistic Intelligence and Critical Thinking on the Students' Report Writing," *Advances in Language and Literary Studies*, vol. 9, no. 6, p. 21, 2018, doi: 10.7575/aialc.all.v9n.6p.21.
- [24] T. Trisno, R. Amini, and I. Irdamurni, "The Effect Of Problem Solving Method on Motivation and Learning Mathematic Results of Class V Sdn 29 Saok Laweh Kabupaten Solok," *International Journal of Educational Dynamics*, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 303–308, 2018, doi: 10.24036/ijeds.v1i1.69.
- [25] N. Septantiningtyas, J. Juhji, A. Sutarma, A. Rahman, N. Sa'adah, and Nawisa, "Implementation of Google Meet Application in the Learning of Basic Science in the Covid-19 Pandemic Period of Student Learning Interests," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1779, no. 1, 2021, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/1779/1/012068.
- [26] U. Hasanah and A. Kamaludin, "The Influence of Quantum Teaching and Learning (QTL) Model on Interests and Learning Outcomes of Chemistry," *Jurnal Pendidikan Sains (Jps)*, vol. 9, no. 1, p. 97, 2021, doi: 10.26714/jps.9.1.2021.97-103.
- [27] S. Nuraisyah, R. D. Harahap, and D. A. Harahap, "Analysis of Internet Media Use of Student Biology Learning Interest During COVID-19," *Jurnal Penelitian Pendidikan IPA*, vol. 7, no. 2, p. 213, 2021, doi: 10.29303/jppipa.v7i2.624.
- [28] A. Amiruddin, N. Nurdin, and M. Ali, "Islamic Education Teacher Communication Strategy in Increasing Students 'Learning Interest," *International Journal of Contemporary Islamic Education*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 41–61, 2021, doi: 10.24239/ijciied.vol3.iss1.31.
- [29] T. Tanti, D. A. Kurniawan, B. Syefrinando, M. Daryanto, and R. S. Fitriani, "Identification of students attitudes towards natural sciences at Adhyaksa 1 Junior High School, Jambi City," *Journal of Education and Learning (EduLearn)*, vol. 15, no. 1, pp. 19–26, 2021, doi: 10.11591/edulearn.v15i1.16377.
- [30] A. Sudrajat, V. Iasha, and F. Femayati, "The Influence of the Use of Cooperative Learning Model Jigsaw & Two Stay Two Stray and the Learning Interest Result on 5th Grade Social Science," in *ICEAP Proceeding Book Vol 2*, Dec. 2018, vol. 2, pp. 28–33, doi: 10.26499/iceap.v2i1.92.
- [31] A. Nanda, D. B. B. Mohapatra, A. P. K. Mahapatra, A. P. K. Mahapatra, and A. P. K. Mahapatra, "Multiple comparison test by Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD): Do the confident level control type I error," *International Journal of Statistics and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 59–65, 2021, doi: 10.22271/math.2021.v6.i1a.636.
- [32] B. Hariadi, "Web-Based Cooperative Learning, Learning Styles, And Student's Learning Outcomes," *Cakrawala*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 153–164, 2015.
- [33] I. Ismail, "The Implementation of Jigsaw Type Cooperative Learning Model to Improve Student Learning Outcomes of Senior High School Seulimun in Aceh Besar Regency," *Budapest International Research and Critics in Linguistics and Education (BirLE) Journal*, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 1267–1273, 2020, doi: 10.33258/birle.v3i3.1164.
- [34] S. Turgut and I. G. Turgut, "The Effects of Cooperative Learning on Mathematics Achievement in Turkey: A Meta-Analysis Study," *International Journal of Instruction*, vol. 11, no. 3, pp. 663–680, 2018.
- [35] Surifah, "Comparison of effectiveness of cooperative learning model Student Teams Achievement Divisions (Stad) and Tipe Think-Pair-Share (Tps) on junior hghigh school," *Jurnal Pengajaran MIPA*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 125–132, 2015.
- [36] M. Lourel, N. Gueguen, A. Pascual, and F. Mouda, "The Effect-Size: A Simple Methodology for Determining and Evaluating the 'Effect-Size,'" *Psychology*, vol. 02, no. 06, pp. 631–632, 2011, doi: 10.4236/psych.2011.26096.
- [37] C. O. Fritz, P. E. Morris, and J. J. Richler, "Effect size estimates: Current use, calculations, and interpretation," *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, vol. 141, no. 1, pp. 2–18, 2012, doi: 10.1037/a0024338.
- [38] S. M. Glass GV, McGaw B, *Meta-analysis in social research*. Newbury Park-London-New Delhi: Newbury Park: Sage Publications, 1981.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Mamik Suendarti is an Associate Professor at Indraprasta University PGRI Jakarta. Obtained a bachelor's degree (S1) in 1996 Department of Land Conversion, from National Development University 'Veteran' Surabaya, S2 in 1998 Department of Land and Water Management from Gajah Mada University Yogyakarta, S3 in 2004 majoring in Natural Resources and Environmental Management from Bogor Agricultural Institute. Experience in the world of college, in addition to being a lecturer since 1999 in several universities for undergraduate programs, she has also held structural positions in Private Universities, as Dean, Assistant Dean, and head of departments. Currently as a permanent lecturer of the Graduate Faculty of Indraprasta University PGRI Jakarta, and serves as Dean of the Graduate Faculty of Indraprasta University PGRI Jakarta. She can be contacted at email: suendarti@gmail.com.

Virgana is an Associate Professor at Indraprasta University PGRI Jakarta, was born in Padang, Indonesia, in September 16, 1955. Obtained a bachelor's degree (S1) in educational Mathematics from IKIP Jakarta Indonesia in 1980, the M.A (Master of Arts) degree in special education from State University of Virginia (UVa), Virginia, USA, and Norwegian Institute for Special education, Oslo, Norway in 1988, and Dr degree in Educational Management from UNJ Jakarta in 2010. Since 2009, Lecturer at Universitas Indrapasta PGRI Jakarta. He can be contacted at email: virganaunindra@gmail.com.